

CHALLENGES OF SCHOOL MANAGERS' E-LEADERSHIP PRACTICES IN RELATION TO TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE: BASIS FOR DEVELOPING AN INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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Challenges of School Managers' E-Leadership Practices in Relation to Teachers' Performance: Basis for Developing an Intervention Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered by school managers in their e-leadership practices in relation to teacher's performance for school year 2022-2023 in all public secondary schools in District II of School Division Office of Quezon City, which served as the basis for an intervention program. Descriptive-correlational type was utilized in this study with survey questionnaire as the data gathering instrument. The respondents of the study were the 29 administrators and 29 teachers from all public secondary schools in District II of School Division Office of Quezon City. The extent of challenges encountered by school managers in their e-leadership practices in terms of school calendar activities, learning strategies, learning modalities and teacher's development obtained an over-all weighted mean of 1.96 with verbal interpretation of moderate extent while the extent of challenges encountered by school managers in their e-leadership practices as perceived by the teachers obtained an over-all weighted mean of 2.61 with verbal interpretation of high extent. Likewise, there was a significant difference in the perceptions of school managers and teacher respondents on the extent of challenges encountered by school managers in their e-leadership practice. Meanwhile, the level of the teacher's performance based on the result of the IPCRF for school year 2022-2023 obtained an over-all weighted mean score of 4.70 with verbal interpretation of outstanding. Furthermore, was a weak relationship between the teachers' performance and the extent of challenges encountered by school managers as perceived by school managers themselves.

Keywords: *infographics, competency-based, Science*

Introduction

In compliance to the DepEd Order 37 Series of 2022 entitled Suspension of Classes Due to Disaster and Calamity, the Quezon City School Division Office (SDO) issued Memorandum 511 series of 2024 adjusting the learning modality to limited face to face and asynchronous modes due to extreme heat. In this situation, e-leadership among school managers is indispensable in order to ensure the continuity of the teaching and learning process and other important aspects in school management.

It is the duty of leaders to utilize digital tools to create transparent, meaningful, engaging, and inspiring school cultures as society becomes more and more reliant on technology. To foster increasing achievement and a greater sense of community pride in the work being done in the classrooms, a change in school leadership must begin immediately.

E - leadership is a phrase that combines "leadership" with the letter "e" which stands for items related to the internet, electronics and virtual environment. It refers to a person's capacity to motivate or sway the subordinates under his/her control to accomplish organizational objectives in virtual platforms. Contextually, it refers to the development of leadership in the setting of a remote workplace where work is done via information technology. This means that managers must modify their practices, attitudes, and behaviors in order to ensure the business performs well over the long run (Contreras et al., 2020).

However, there were certain challenges with the switch from traditional to e-leadership. Many school administrators nationwide stated that availability of digital devices for students, dependable and adequate internet, and instructors' technical proficiency and familiarity with remote teaching pedagogies were among the obstacles that hampered remote teaching and supervision using Information and Communication Technology (ICT).

Based on the researcher's observations and personal experiences in the district 2 public secondary school in Quezon City, there was a need to study the challenges encountered by school managers in their e-leadership practices and what would be its effect on the teacher's performance. Especially nowadays that in order to manage their school and their subordinates, school managers use e-leadership, which has greatly facilitated communication.

Consequently, the process of e-leadership adaptation in virtual work environments might present numerous difficulties. School managers must gain a deeper understanding of the organizational structure, including its capabilities, shortcomings, and strengths. Improved work-life balance, flexibility, and social learning and knowledge are also necessary for the successful use of e-leadership. Moreover, communication and information dysfunction might occur, making it difficult for school managers to develop employee trust.

The researcher believed that the challenges encountered by the school managers would help them to create and develop new strategies to improve their e-leadership practices which is very essential in this present time when natural catastrophe due to climate change occur, health issues and many other factors happening all over the world that surely affect the educational system. In this way, it could be assured that education would continue amidst all situations.

Finally, knowing these challenges, the researcher created an intervention program that would solve and provide additional input on e-leadership of school managers and teachers as well.

Research Questions

This study attempted to determine the extent challenges encountered by school managers on their e-leadership practices in relation to teacher's performance for school year 2022-2023 in all public secondary schools in District II of School Division Office of Quezon City, which served as the basis for an intervention program. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the extent of the challenges encountered by school managers in their e-leadership practices as perceived by the teachers and school managers themselves in terms of the following aspects?
 - 1.1. school calendar activities;
 - 1.2. learning strategies;
 - 1.3. learning modalities; and
 - 1.4. teachers' development?
2. Is there a significant difference between the perceptions of the two groups of respondents on the extent of challenges encountered by the school managers in their e-leadership practices on the aforementioned aspects?
3. What is the level of the teacher's performance based on the result of the IPCRF for school year 2022-2023 in terms of the following criteria?
 - 3.1. content knowledge and pedagogy;
 - 3.2. learning environment and diversity of learners;
 - 3.3. curriculum and planning;
 - 3.4. assessment and reporting; and
 - 3.5. personal growth and professional development?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of the challenges encountered by the school managers and their e-leadership practices and the teachers' performance?
5. What intervention program can be developed based on the results of the study?

Literature Review

The term "e-leadership" refers to those who carry out all of their leadership responsibilities and activities via electronic means. Therefore, the context in which each type of leader functions is the primary factor that differentiates the traditional leader from the e-leader. An e-leader is a person who is capable of influencing other people through the use of technical means and initiating a behavior and performance of individuals and groups in order to accomplish certain objectives (Bouassaba, 2022).

Aggarwal (2019), in his article entitled, "E-leadership: A New and Modern Style of Leadership", emphasized that since e-leadership involves a leader using ICT and electronic media to guide followers, it could be a significant management tool. The electronic media has taken the place of traditional face-to-face communication.

Relatively, Chang et al. (2022), in their journal entitled, "E-leadership Analysis during Pandemic Outbreak to Enhanced Learning in Higher Education", discussed that a successful organization needs leaders who are willing to take on leadership roles. Taking high quality innovative ideas and spreading them throughout society is crucial to success. A strong leadership position enables distance education programs to accomplish their objective successfully and efficiently while remaining responsive to the needs of their beneficiaries and users.

In addition, In the remote working environment, leaders must prioritize effective communication and coordination among team members to minimize miscommunication. In this context, e-communication was vital in using basic technology tools like email and videoconferencing to facilitate communication and contribute to the overall performance (Roman, et.al, 2019).

Moreover, in the article of Sunarsi et al. (2020) entitled "Effect of e-Leadership Style, Organizational Commitment and Service Quality towards Indonesian School Performance", discussed that e-leadership plays a critical role in maintaining and enhancing educational quality, which has far-reaching implications for a country's well-being including economic prosperity, public health and social well-being.

On the other hand, the study of Tahir et al. (2021), entitled "Evaluating the Practice of ICT-Based E-Leadership: The Experiences of Private-Based Secondary Teachers," investigated how teachers and school administrators may use technology advancements to create an e-leadership platform. Findings revealed that the school principals had used ICT-based e-leadership practices to conduct online meetings with teachers and disseminate relevant information on the school's administrative tasks. Most importantly, the principals have used e-leadership on a regular basis in planning and developing strategic school-improvement plans with teachers.

Another related study was the study of Mustajab et al. (2020) entitled "Covid: What are the Challenges and Opportunities for e-Leadership. This paper's key finding was that many organizations were unprepared for this situation, making e-leadership a very effective tool for maintaining organizational performance. Leaders could adapt their style through social learning and surmount the

obstacles they must overcome to become e-leaders. Furthermore, they also found that female leaders are typically more knowledgeable than male leaders when it comes to e-leadership.

Comighud (2019) found out that there was also a significant difference shown in the extent of school heads' performance management mechanisms and teachers' job performance when the former and the latter were respectively grouped according to their profile items as to the length of experience, educational attainment, and position held. It concluded that there is a strong and significant relationship between the extent of performance.

Methodology

Research Design

The method of research used in this study was the descriptive-correlational type. According to Combers (2019), descriptive research aimed to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation or phenomenon. This study utilized descriptive-correlational research to determine the extent of challenges encountered by school managers on their e-leadership practices in relation to teacher performance, which served as the basis for the intervention program.

Respondents

The sources of data were the six (6) principals, six (6) Department Heads, seventeen (17) Master Teachers and twenty-nine (29) teachers of all secondary schools of District 2 of Quezon City, namely: Batasan Hills National High School, Bagong Silangan High School, Commonwealth High School, Holy Spirit National High School, Justice Cecilia Munoz Palma High School and Judge Feliciano Belmonte Sr. High School. They were purposively chosen.

Instrument

The survey questionnaire was employed as the main instrument for gathering information on the respondents in this study. The researcher constructed the survey questionnaire. This was validated by two (2) head teacher, one (1) master teacher, two (2) subject teachers and two (3) professors of Marikina Polytechnic College.

Procedure

After the research proposal was approved by the defense panel, the survey questionnaire was developed and had it checked by the thesis adviser and validated by eight validator experts. After this, permission to conduct the study was requested from the Schools Divisions Superintendent of Quezon City and the principals of all six secondary public schools in District 2 through a formal letter. After getting the permission, the researcher personally distributed the survey questionnaire with an attached approved letters from SDO QC and Principals to school managers and teachers and waited for one week for the retrieval of the research instrument.

Following the completion of the survey, the replies of the participants were analyzed. The data were handled and totaled with the highest confidentiality with the assistance of a statistician. Following the data collection, the researcher compiled, summarized, encoded, tabulated, and totaled the responses from the respondents. The results were then interpreted and analyzed.

Ethical Considerations

In compliance with Republic Act 10173 also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012 that aims to protect personal data in information and communications systems both in the government and the private sector. It covers the processing of personal information and sensitive personal information and sets, as its basic premise, the grant of direct consent by a data subject before data processing of personal information is allowed.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Extent of the Challenges Encountered by School Managers in their E- Leadership Practices as Perceived by the Teachers and School Managers Themselves

Table 1. *Extent of Challenges Encountered by School Managers in their E- Leadership Practices as Perceived by the Teachers and School Managers Themselves in terms of School Calendar Activities*

A. School Calendar Activities	School Managers		Teachers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. encounter difficulty in identifying flexible dates and time for the school calendar	2.00	ME	2.75	HE
2. have a hard time in identifying a common time for the teachers to attend meetings.	1.86	ME	2.54	HE
3. meet a difficulty in making individuals work collectively.	1.76	ME	2.61	HE
4. find it hard to create a culture that allows all the voices of the teachers to be heard.	1.72	LE	2.64	HE
5. have difficulty in providing feedback immediately through video conferencing.	1.86	ME	2.44	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	1.84	ME	2.61	HE
Standard Deviation		0.76		0.69

The data highlighted that school managers face average challenges in various aspects of school calendar activities. However, teachers perceived these challenges to be big compared to school managers. It can be deduced from the results that both school managers and teachers perceive difficulty in identifying flexible dates and times for the school calendar as the most challenging practice related to school calendar activities.

These findings concurred with Mustajab et al. (2020), that when they have to postpone typical tasks like setting up teacher schedules or doing performance reviews at unexpected times, executives of educational organizations find it difficult to manage their work hours.

Table 2. *Extent of Challenges Encountered by School Managers in their E-Leadership Practices as Perceived by the Teachers and School Managers Themselves in terms of Learning Strategies*

<i>B. Learning Strategies</i>	<i>School Managers</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. have difficulty in dealing with the teachers and students with different learning styles.	1.93	ME	2.61	HE
2. am challenged by those who do not actively participate in the discussion.	2.07	ME	2.68	ME
3. experience difficulties in encouraging teachers to use e-learning strategies.	1.69	ME	2.50	ME
4. have issues of motivating the teachers, students, and other stakeholders in discussing and presenting concepts.	1.62	LE	2.50	ME
5. encounter problems on equal access of resources by teachers, students, and parents.	2.21	ME	2.81	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	1.90	ME	2.61	HE
Standard Deviation	0.59		0.69	

Based on the table shown above, both school managers and teachers identified the equal access of resources by teachers, students, and parents as the most challenging practice regarding learning strategies. This finding suggested that ensuring equitable access to resources poses a significant challenge for school managers. It implies that differences in access to resources among different stakeholders may hinder effective teaching and learning processes.

The abovementioned results were reinforced by Mustajab et al. (2020). According to them, e-leadership was a communication method that would undoubtedly differ from direct communication in that it will entail the use of digital or virtual media like computers and the internet.

Table 3. *Extent of Challenges Encountered by School Managers in their E-Leadership Practices as Perceived by the Teachers and School Managers Themselves in terms of Learning Modalities*

<i>C. Learning Modalities</i>	<i>School Managers</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. have difficulty in adjusting to the varied technical capabilities of the teachers, students, and parents, as regards to online learning.	1.86	ME	2.61	HE
2. meet difficulties in identifying opportunities for teachers, students, and presents to interact with each other in a social setting.	1.90	ME	2.61	HE
3. have difficulty in dealing on lack of necessary resources, such as reliable internet connectivity, devices for students, and up-to-date software.	2.41	ME	2.64	HE
4. have a hard time bridging the gap on the varying levels of digital literacy or competence among teachers, students, and parents.	2.14	ME	2.71	HE
5. have difficulty on maintaining student's engagement and motivation in virtual or hybrid learning settings or in any online environment.	2.28	ME	2.75	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	2.12	ME	2.66	HE
Standard Deviation	0.68		0.73	

This finding highlighted the critical importance of adequate resources for effective implementation of online learning modalities, highlighting the need for strategic interventions to address resource gaps and ensure equitable access to technology for all stakeholders on the part of school managers. On the part of the teacher, the need for more engaging activities to sustain the motivation and retention of the students in a virtual classroom is a must.

Mustajab et al. (2020) endorsed the preceding outcome. The leaders of the business have benefited from the evolution of information technology for internal communication and coordination, as they attested to the fact that mediation of communication currently offers a wide range of options.

The data presented in table 4 indicate that school managers face minimal challenges in several aspects of teachers' development. On the other hand, teachers perceived these challenges to be big, except for the difficulty in encouraging attendance at ICT training, which is rated as common.

The result was supported by Mustajab et al. (2020). According to them the training and development programs were conducted online for the team members. E – leaders monitor the work of all the individuals and provided them constructive feedback so that they were motivated to perform well and improve the performance with the leader's assistance.

Table 4. *Extent of Challenges Encountered by School Managers in their E-Leadership Practices as Perceived by the Teachers and School Managers Themselves in terms of Teacher's Development*

<i>D. Teachers Development</i>	<i>School Managers</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
1. experience problems in teachers' technical skills development.	2.00	ME	2.46	HE
2. difficulty in encouraging teaches to attend training on ICT.	1.79	ME	2.29	ME
3. have encountered problem in budgeting and allocating resources for professional development programs, workshops, and training materials.	2.17	ME	2.79	HE
4. have difficulty in finding time for teachers to participate in professional development activities due to busy schedules and teaching responsibilities.	1.83	ME	2.64	HE
5. have a hard time in catering the diverse needs and preferences of teaching staffs with varying experience levels, subject areas, and teaching styles.	2.00	ME	2.57	HE
Overall Weighted Mean	1.96	ME	2.55	HE
Standard Deviation	0.73		0.64	

Test of Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of Challenges Encountered by the School Managers in their E-leadership Practices

Table 5. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of Challenges Encountered by the School Managers in their E-leadership Practices on School Calendar Activities*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>OWM</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>Computed t value</i>	<i>Critical t value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. School Managers	1.84	0.76	4.04	2.00	Reject the H ₀	Significant
2. Teachers	2.61	0.69				

This finding highlights the importance of open communication and collaboration between managers and teachers to address differences and develop effective strategies for managing school calendars that meet the needs of all stakeholders. Thus, the result was supported by Mustajab et al (2020). Nearly all company leaders reported that they find it extremely difficult to manage their employees' time at work. This issue stems from the government-imposed "lockdown" situation, which requires all businesses to send workers' home.

Table 6. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of Challenges Encountered by the School Managers in their E-leadership Practices on Learning Strategies*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>OWM</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>Computed t value</i>	<i>Critical t value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. School Managers	1.90	0.59	4.27	2.00	Reject the H ₀	Significant
2. Teachers	2.61	0.69				

This finding highlights the importance of recognizing and addressing these differences in perception to enhance collaboration and alignment between school managers and teachers in implementing effective learning strategies. It suggests a need for closer communication and shared decision-making processes to ensure that educational objectives are met, and challenges are effectively addressed within the school community. The abovementioned result was reinforced by Mustajab et al. (2020), that leaders of educational organizations give the opinion that maintaining trust generally aimed to maintain job satisfaction and productivity of teachers by motivating them and giving full rights of teachers

Table 7. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of Challenges Encountered by the School Managers in their E-leadership Practices on Learning Modalities*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>OWM</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>Computed t value</i>	<i>Critical t value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. School Managers	2.12	0.68	3.02	2.00	Reject the H ₀	Significant
2. Teachers	2.66	0.73				

This finding highlights the importance of acknowledging and addressing these perceptual differences to ensure effective collaboration and decision-making in e-leadership practices aimed at addressing challenges in learning modalities within educational institutions. Tahir et al. (2021) supported the above results. They affirmed that tests show that there were significant differences in teacher's perceptions of using the ICT-based applications within their respective schools based on teaching experience and age.

Table 8. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Perceptions of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Extent of Challenges Encountered by the School Managers in their E-leadership Practices on Teachers' Development*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>OWM</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>Computed t value</i>	<i>Critical t value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. School Managers	1.96	0.73	3.35	2.00	Reject the H ₀	Significant
2. Teachers	2.55	0.64				

This finding highlights the need for improved communication and collaboration between managers and teachers to align their understanding and address challenges effectively in supporting teacher development through e-leadership practices within educational settings.

The aforementioned results are consistent with the research conducted by Pagatpatan (2019) and this study, which found no evidence of a meaningful relationship between the effectiveness of teachers and the digital leadership of school administrators.

Level of the Teacher's Performance Based on the Result of the IPCRF for School Year 2022-2023

Table 9. *Level of the teacher's performance based on the result of the IPCRF for school year 2022-2023 in terms of Content, Knowledge and Pedagogy*

	<i>Content Knowledge and Pedagogy</i>	<i>Teachers</i>	
		<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Applied knowledge of content within the across curriculum and learning areas.	5.00	O
2.	Use a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills.	4.70	O
3.	Applied a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills	4.16	VS
Weighted Mean		4.62	O
Standard Deviation		0.25	

Their performance was notably very satisfactory in terms of applying a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, along with other higher-order thinking skills. This interpretation highlighted the importance of recognizing teachers' strengths and areas for growth, which can inform targeted professional development efforts to further enhance teaching effectiveness and student outcomes.

This was supported by Mustajab (2020), the implementation and monitoring of the curriculum become easy, and the decision-making is also improved as the decisions are made based on data.

Table 10. *Level of the teacher's performance based on the result of the IPCRF for school year 2022-2023 in terms of Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners*

	<i>Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners</i>	<i>Teachers</i>	
		<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Managed classroom structure to engage learners, individually, or in groups, in meaningful explorations and discovery.	4.57	O
2.	Managed learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environment.	4.84	O
3.	Used differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address learners' gender needs.	4.73	O
Weighted Mean		4.71	O
Standard Deviation		0.29	

This finding highlighted the commendable efforts of teachers in creating inclusive and effective learning environments that cater to the needs of all students. Moreover, this also highlights the significant contributions of teachers to the educational process and their commitment to facilitating optimal learning experiences for all students.

Tahir et al. (2021) attested to the above result that the use of technology improves the teachers' hard and soft skills, which in turn has a good impact on the performance and expertise of the students. Hence, the teaching and learning process becomes truly beneficial for the students.

Table 11. *Level of the teacher's performance based on the result of the IPCRF for school year 2022-2023 in terms of Curriculum and Planning*

	<i>Curriculum and Planning</i>	<i>Teachers</i>	
		<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Planned, managed and implemented developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum.	4.93	O
2.	Participated in collegial discussions that use teacher and learner feedback to enrich teaching practices.	4.82	O
3.	Selected, developed, organized, and used appropriate teaching and learning resources including ICT to address learning.	4.77	O
Weighted Mean		4.84	O
Standard Deviation		0.23	

Overall, teachers' performance in these areas is outstanding. The results imply that teachers exhibit exemplary proficiency in several key aspects of their teaching practice in terms of curriculum and planning. Thus, the outstanding performance of teachers in these critical areas, emphasizes their dedication to effective teaching practices in curriculum and planning as well as achieving student

success.

According to Kousar et al. (2020), e-leadership positively impacts the teacher's performance. Teachers may face issues due to inadequate resources, improper training, technical faults, and improper guidance, the satisfaction level of the teachers with e-leadership practices is impacted.

Table 12. *Level of the teacher's performance based on the result of the IPCRF for school year 2022-2023 in terms of Assessment and Reporting*

		<i>Assessment and Reporting</i>	
		<i>Teachers</i>	
		<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Designed, selected, organized and used diagnostic, formative and summative assessment strategies.	4.84	O
2.	Monitored and evaluated learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data.	4.75	O
3.	Communicated promptly and clearly the learners' needs, progress and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians.	4.57	O
		Weighted Mean	4.72 O
		Standard Deviation	0.20

The results indicated that teachers exhibit remarkable proficiency in several key areas related to the assessment and reporting of their performance. Overall, this highlighted the exceptional performance of teachers in assessment and reporting, showcasing their dedication to facilitating student success and fostering meaningful engagement with key stakeholders in the educational process.

The abovementioned results were reinforced by Maisyaroh et al. (2020), that the teacher is one of the most important factors in determining student learning results.

Table 13. *Level of the teacher's performance based on the result of the IPCRF for school year 2022-2023 in terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development*

		<i>Personal Growth and Professional Development</i>	
		<i>Teachers</i>	
		<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
1.	Applied personal philosophy of teaching that is learner-centered.	4.43	VS
2.	Set professional goals based of Philippines Professional Standards for Teachers	4.93	O
3.	Performed various related works/activities that contribute to the teaching learning process.	4.47	VS
		Weighted Mean	4.61 O
		Standard Deviation	0.32

Overall, these findings suggested that teachers have made significant steps in their personal and professional development, aligning with the expectations outlined in the IPCRF for the school year 2022-2023.

Sunarsi et al. (2020) supported the above results, as school performance is achieved and demonstrated through work ability and work results that are not only done individually but also in teamwork in organizations. Performance is the work achieved by a person in carrying out the tasks assigned to him based on skills, experience, seriousness, and time.

Conclusions

The study's findings led to the following conclusions: School managers encounter minimal challenges across various aspects, such as school calendar activities, learning strategies, learning modalities, and teacher development, while teachers perceive these challenges to be great. The school managers and teachers have different points of view regarding the challenges faced by the school managers in their e-leadership practices. The teachers consistently demonstrated outstanding performance during the school year 2022-2023. The challenges encountered by the school managers do not affect the teacher's performance all across criteria in IPCRF for the school year 2022-2023. An intervention program of training activities is needed to address the challenges encountered.

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